

o'quvchilar tashabbus ko'rsatishlariga imkoniyatlar yaratilishi, kichik guruh, katta guruh bo'lib ishlash uchun topshiriqlar berish, yozma ishlar bajarish va boshqa metodlardan iborat bo'lib, ular ta'lim-tarbiyaviy ishlar samaradorligini oshirishda o'ziga xos ahamiyatga ega." [1. M., Tilavova. 151]

ФОЙДАЛАНИЛГАН АДАБИЁТЛАР:

1. M., Tilavova . Texnologiya va uni o'qitish metodikasi. "Durdona" nashriyoti Buxoro – 2021
2. S. Endler, P. Kühr. "Projektarbeit-Projektkompetenzen handlung-orientiert erlernen." Verlag Europa Lehrmittel, Haan-Gruiten 2010.
3. Anna Maria, Korte. "Projektarbeit-fit für Ausbildung und Studium: Lern- und Arbeitsheft zur Projektarbeit" Merkur Verlag 2010.
4. Projektorientiertes Lernen im DaF-Unterricht .Katharina Zobel <http://lernenarchiv.bildung.hessen.de/...>
5. <https://www.meinunterricht.de/blog/projektunterricht-projektarbeit-schule-themen-ideen-beispiele/>

VISUAL ELEMENTS AVAILABLE IN FICTIONAL FILMS AS ADDITIONAL TOOL FOR IMPROVING LANGUAGE SKILLS IN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: This study focuses on the use of visual aids such as gestures, facial expressions, and postures in fictional films as a means of improving language skills in medical terminology. The paper highlights the significance of non-verbal language in medical communication and the role that visual cues play in enhancing

effective communication between medical professionals and patients. The study explores how fictional films provide a unique tool for learners to observe and analyze medical communication skills in real-life settings. The research concludes that the use of visual aids in fictional films can significantly improve language proficiency in medical terminology and promote accurate and effective communication between healthcare professionals and patients.

Keywords: fictional films, interactive learning, English language

With the continuous growth and progress in the field of medicine, the demand for effective communication between medical professionals and patients has increased rapidly. Communication plays a vital role in the medical field, not only in terms of discussing diagnosis, treatment, and prevention strategies, but also in providing psychological support to patients, as well as their families. However, due to the complexity of the medical terminology and procedures, language barriers pose significant problems in communicating effectively. To overcome the challenges of language barriers, the use of visual aids such as gestures, facial expressions, and postures in medical films can be an effective tool to enhance communication and improve language mastery in medicine. Chuprakova expresses a general thesis, explaining: “extralinguistic factors of speech are integral parts of the speech process itself (communicative act), without which speech is unthinkable [1].

Gestures, mimicry, and postures are an important aspect of non-verbal language communication. In particular, medical professionals use them as a part of the standard practice while communicating medical information to patients. However, frequently, medical students and professionals lack competence in using these non-verbal language tools effectively, and this is where films can be an invaluable source of training.

Films have the potential to enhance language learning, particularly when it comes to medical terminology. They are ideal resources for learners to observe and analyze medical communication skills in authentic situations. Medical films

provide a comprehensive illustration of medical terminology and procedures in real-life settings and offer important cues that enrich non-verbal language communication skills. Cognitive-pragmatic theory understands communicative competence as the ability to draw correct inferences in order to recognize a partner's communicative intent [2]. All these phenomena increase semantically significant information, but not at the expense of additional speech inclusions, but at the expense of “near speech” techniques [3].

Medical films offer numerous advantages that promote efficient communication between medical professionals and patients. The inclusion of visual aids of gestures, facial expressions, and postures in medical films can help learners understand and interpret the non-verbal language used in medical practice. It offers a unique opportunity to observe how skilled professionals use non-verbal communication techniques to convey information. Observing and analyzing the healthcare professional's communication behavior assists in developing essential skills necessary for effective communication in the medical field.

Moreover, the film's invaluable role in developing the medical language proficiency of novice practitioners is significant. Using films in language learning encourages vocabulary acquisition in addition to comprehension of medical topics. It provides learners with the opportunity to learn new medical terms in the context of realistic situations. It also promotes accurate and effective communication. Consequently, the use of films in language learning can significantly improve a healthcare professional's diagnostic skills, decision-making abilities, and overall competence in medical communication.

In conclusion, the use of visual aids such as gestures, mimicry, and postures in medical films is an effective tool for enhancing communication skills in the medical profession. Medical films produce an authentic representation of medical procedures and terminology and provide an excellent resource for learners to acquire necessary knowledge and skills to communicate effectively with patients. Their use enables learners to interpret non-verbal language cues accurately, develop vocabulary, and promote their understanding of complex medical

terminologies. Therefore, it is essential that medical language teachers, educators, and trainers consider visual aids in medical films as an additional tool for language learning for medical practice.

REFERENCES

1. E.V. Chuprakova, Linguistic and extralinguistic aspects of translation // <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/lingvisticheskie-i-ekstralingvisticheskie-aspekty-perevoda>
2. Bara, B.G. Cognitive pragmatics: mental processes of communication // Cambridge: MIT Press. (2010).
3. Functions of Nonverbal Communication Business Psychology // Course of lectures <http://www.bibliotekar.ru/psihologia-4/173.htm>

INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA CHET TILINI O'RGANISH SAMARADORLIGIN OSHIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy ta'limni tashkil etishga qo'yiladigan muhim talablardan biri ortiqcha ruhiy va jismoniy kuch sarf etmay, qisqa vaqt ichida yuksak natijalarga erishishdir. Ushbu maqolada innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida chet tilini o'rganish samaradorligini oshirishda asosan nimalarga e'tibor berish kerakligi, unda o'qituvchining roli haqida yoritilgan. Shuningdek, til o'rganishda talabalarni fikrlashga undovchi ayrim ijodiy vazifalardan namunalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy ta'lim, pedagogik texnologiyalar, innovatsion usul, talabalar, o'qituvchi.

Xorij pedagogik texnologiyalarini o'rganish, uni taxlil etib, ijobiy tomonlaridan unumli foydalanish shubhasiz ta'lim sifatini oshiruvchi muhim